

ANALYSIS AND MITIGATE OIL EXTRACTION RATE USING HOUSE OF RISK METHOD

Danang Adi Kuncoro¹, Rr Anya Oktarahmawati¹,

Danang Amangkurat Mas¹, Dwi Handayani¹

¹Industrial Engineering Departement, Universitas Islam Indonesia,
Jalan Kaliurang Km 14,4, Yogyakarta, Indonesia 55584

Abstract

The increasing development of the palm oil industry in Indonesia demands palm oil producers to constantly improve their productivity. Overall, Indonesia has produced 33 million tons in 2016 and is predicted to increase annually. The number of risks causing the failure of the yield target which impacts on the production of palm oil resulted in the company having to do the evaluation so that the company can still compete in producing palm oil, therefore risk mitigation is needed to reduce the risk of the cause of yield incapacity. The risks need to be identified and mitigated to minimize the risks. In this research, the house of risk model is used to identify the cause and effect of the risk. After analyzing the house of risk model with two phases. The identified risks are 13 incidence risk and 9 events with the dominant priority being the priority of handling. The risk priorities based on House of Risk Phase 1 results are A11, A10, A9, A14, A2, A18, A13, A, 16 and A1. From the predominant risk, the first priority handling is on P4, which is more strictly inspected incoming fruits.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2538891

1. Introduction

Indonesia is one of the countries that produce palm oil (CPO) with a total production of 33 million tons in 2016 [1] . The palm oil industry is experiencing rapid growth from year to year. It is predicted that the demand for palm oil from Indonesia will increase from 33 million to 35 tons in 2016 [1] which is a national CPO production. At present the palm oil industry contributes greatly to the economy in Indonesia. It is estimated that palm oil sales will reach USD 14.7 million in 2016 [1].

The increasing demand makes the company continue to try to increase the amount of production and the quality of palm oil production. Oil Extraction rate is one measure of the success of palm oil mills in processing fresh fruit bunches. Losses in the production process become very important as target losses in each production process where losses can also be a risk of yield not being achieved in the process fresh fruit bunches production. In 2017 the average Oil Extraction rate is still at an average of 19%. These results are the results of the average annual yield.

Uncertainty of achievement target the company's OER 20% of the total processed TBS make the company continue to evaluate the cause or risks that cause OER not to be achieved. This will greatly affect the performance of the company in achieving the yield target which is the target of the company. So that the risks of non-achievement need to be carried out an analysis of the causes of non-achievement and it is necessary to mitigate the risks that occur so that the company is able to compete both in quality and increase the quality of the final product in the form of crude palm oil so that the OER target can be achieved.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Risk and Risk Management

Risks can be defined as potential that can be detrimental to the results that deviate from the expected [2]. To identify the risks that exist in a company risk management can be done. To obtain optimal results is one of the objectives of Risk Management. [2] Risk management can be done when designing a system and when a system is running. Risk Management is an effective way to reduce the adverse consequences of extreme events and play an important role in changing the changes that occur [3]. Risk management is a feasible way to deal with uncertainty from a deterministic one, often called a scientific approach [4].

2.2 House of Risk

One method that can be used to carry out risk management is the House of Risk. House of Risk a model is one tool that can help overcome risk uncertainty by distinguishing better probability with the level of risk that occurs [4]. House of risk is a method based on the idea that a proactive supply chain management must endeavor to focus on preventive actions, for example reducing the probability of a risk agent occurring [5]. House of risk can be identified several parameters including the number of risky events, the cause of the risk, the value of Aggregate Risk Potential (ARP), the prevention or mitigation measures, and the correlation between the underlying risk mitigation measures to be performed [5]. In the House of Risk method, there are two parts, namely House of Risk 1 and House of Risk 2 [6]. House of Risk 1 is used to determine which risk sources are prioritized to take precautionary measures while the House of Risk 2 is conducted to provide action by considering effective cost resources [6].

House of Risk 1 consists of risk event identification, occurrence and severity calculations, creating correlation relationship matrix, ARP calculation, and Pareto diagram making and for House of Risk 2 consists of prevention action or mitigation, risk agent correlation and mitigation, total effectiveness calculation mitigation, measuring the degree of difficulty in implementing mitigation, and calculating effectiveness to difficulty ratio, and prioritization rating mitigation [6]

3. Methodology

The method used in the analysis and mitigation is to use a risk management approach and analysis s using House of Risk. In doing so, the following steps are carried out in two phases, the House of risk phase consists of several activities, namely:

3.1. House of Risk Phase 1

Step 1. Mapping process activities

At this stage, the production process will be analyzed from raw materials to finished products and delivered to consumers

Step 2. Risk identification

At this stage, risks will be analyzed in the production process by conducting direct observations and interviews with the company

Step 3. Risk Analysis

This stage is analyzed using a fish bone diagram

Step 4. Determine severity and risk event

Giving severity value and any risk that occurs

Step 5. Determine Occurrence and risk agent

Determine the value of occurrence at every risk that occurs in the process

Step 6. Determine the correlation

This stage is an analysis of the relationship between severity and occurrence and the giving of the relationship window between the two

Step 7. Calculation of aggregate risk potential (ARP)

Perform ARP calculations to determine the rank with the biggest risk

Step 8. Risk Evaluation

Determine the sources of risk that need to be handled

3.2. House of Risk Phase 2

Step 9. Designing a priority risk management strategy

At this stage is the House of risk Phase 2, by determining the priority of follow-up handling.

4. Result and Discussion

In this study conducted in one of the national private oil palm plantation companies. There are several problems that occur, namely not achieving the yield target when producing palm oil. This occurs due to the risk in the process that occurs, therefore it is necessary to do an analysis in order to mitigate the effort the risk of not achieving the target can be minimized. To solve this problem, the House of Risk method is used as a tool to identify the dominant risks that occur and the handling of these risks.

TABLE 9. RISK EVENT

Proses	Risk Event	Code	Severity
Plan	Improper forecasting of demand	E1	3
	Sudden production changes	E2	7
Source	The difference in the actual number of stocks recorded	E3	5
	Incompatibility of raw materials ordered	E4	7
	Incompatibility of the ordered amount	E5	7
	Raw material damage	E6	5
	Defective product	E7	10
Make	Production is delayed	E8	9
	Worker accident	E9	10
	Engine failure	E10	9
	Production is not on target	E11	9
Delivery	Product damage during shipping	E12	7

The data in table 1 shows some of the risks that cause the yield target is not achieved based on the results of direct observations and interviews with the company. Table 1 contains the E 1, E 2 codes, and the confirmation that shows the risk and severity events shows the impact if the risk occurs with a rating from none to dangerous and symbolized by numbers 1 to 10.

TABLE 10. RISK AGENT

No	Risk Agent	Code	Occurance
1	Error in forecasting	A1	7
2	Internal party uncertainty about raw material suppliers	A2	8
3	Lack of raw material supply capacity in warehouses	A3	1
4	Error in recording incoming raw materials	A4	7
5	Lack of coordination between internal parties	A5	6
6	Operator layout is not ergonomic	A6	4

No	Risk Agent	Code	Occurance
7	The supplier's ability to produce fluctuations	A7	7
8	Inadequate raw material storage	A8	6
9	Error sorting raw materials	A9	7
10	Contaminated with other objects (water, sand, etc.)	A10	7
11	Low raw material quality	A11	7
12	Human resource limitation	A12	6
13	A bottleneck occurs	A13	5
14	Problematic machine	A14	5
15	Employees who are not abedient in using PPE according to SOP	A15	4
16	Limitation of engine/equipment capacity	A16	5
17	Late production	A17	6
18	Inaccurate inspection of raw material receipts	A18	7

Table 2 shows the frequency of risks that occur. in table 2 the symbol used to describe the frequency occurs with the symbol A 1, A 2, Ai ... From table 1 and table 2, an analysis of the relationship between the impact and the level of frequency occurs. Aggregate Risk Priority Result. Based on the risk analysis and frequency that occur as shown in table 1 and table 2, then calculating the Aggregate risk priority which results are used as a balance material to determine the priority of risk handlings a tool to calculate the ARP value [6] . Aggregate risk potential can be calculated using the formula in equation 1.

$$ARP_j = O_j \sum S_i R_{ij} \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Information:

- ARP = Agregate Risk Priority value
- Oj = Value of occurrence risk agent
- Si = Value of severuty risk event
- Rij = correlation between risk event and risk agent

From the formula then the calculation results are presented in table 3 below.

TABLE 11. CAUSE OF RISK

	Occurrence	ARP	Rank
A1	7	448	9
A2	8	944	5
A3	1	18	18
A4	7	427	10
A5	6	372	12
A6	4	124	17
A7	7	252	15
A8	6	222	16
A9	7	1253	3
A10	7	1645	2
A11	7	1855	1
A12	6	408	11

	Occurrence	ARP	Rank
A13	5	680	7
A14	5	1235	4
A15	4	360	13
A16	5	570	8
A17	6	288	14
A18	7	735	6

Based on the results of the calculation of table 3, then an analysis is performed using Pareto diagrams to describe the causes and effects of each factor and determine the risks that are prioritized for handling. With the 80:20 rule principle, which fixes 80% of the problem is caused by 20% of the problems that occur. The results of the Pareto diagram can be seen in Figure 2.

FIGURE 1. PARETO DIAGRAM

Then the results in Figure 2, become the top priority for handling. The results are then assessed for the impact and frequency that occur in table 4.

TABLE 12. RISK AGENT

Code	Risk Agent	Oj	Si
A11	Low raw material quality	7	7
A10	Contaminated with other objects (water, sand, etc.)	7	5
A9	Error sorting raw materials	7	7
A14	Problematic machine	5	9
A2	Internal party uncertainty about raw material suppliers	8	7
A18	Inaccurate inspection of raw material receipts	7	5
A13	A bottleneck occurs	5	9
A16	Limitations of engine / equipment capacity	5	9
A1	Error in forecasting	7	3

From Table 4 then as input to identify the location of the risk that occurs based on the level of risk assessment in table 5.

TABLE 13. RISK LEVEL

Risk Level		
Level	Impact (<i>Severity</i>)	Probability (<i>Occurence</i>)
Very Low	1,2,3,4	1,2,3,4
Low	5	5
Medium	6	6
High	7,8	7,8
Very High	9,10	9,10

Impact Matrix

The results of the Impact matrix are based on the implications of table 4 and table 5. These results are the results of the dominant risk mapping. The results of the matrix are presented in table 6.

TABLE 14. IMPACT MATRIX

Level of possibility		Level impact (Severity)				
		1	2	3	4	5
		Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very High
5	Very High					
4	High	A1	A10, A18		A11, A9, A2	
3	Medium					
2	Low					A14, A13, A16
1	Very Low					

Then after the dominant risk is obtained from the calculation and mapping results in table 6. Then the risk management strategy is carried out. Risk strategy can be seen in table 7. In table 7 there is a code as a symbol for each strategy that is carried out. The strategy is used as input material for handling the risk of House of Risk Phase 2 which was previously analyzed by using house of risk phase 1.

TABLE 15. STRATEGY

No	Strategy	Code
1	The supplier is more considering giving fertilizer for fresh fruit bunches (PA1)	PA1
2	How to choose seeds and harvest fresh fruit bunches must be repaired from the supplier (PA2)	PA2
3	Give sanctions to suppliers who deliberately mix raw materials with other goods (PA3)	PA3
4	Inspection upon receipt of tightened raw materials (PA4)	PA4
5	A more adequate tool update for sorting raw materials (PA5)	PA5
6	The engine maintenance time is carried out more continuously (PA6)	PA6

No	Strategy	Code
7	Internal parties are given training to be more professional in a transaction (PA7)	PA7
8	Company sanctions are more clarified to apply (PA8)	PA8
9	Do not rely on experience or instinct in sorting raw materials but must be more accurate in quantity (PA9)	PA9
10	Cycle time balance between work station with one another (PA10)	PA10
11	Adding capacity / engine to the work station that is bottlenecked (PA11)	PA11
12	Production capacity takes into account engine capacity and division of workload on each machine / tool (PA12)	PA12
13	Validating historical data as a reference for forecasting in the future (PA13)	PA13

At the House of risk phase 2, calculations will be performed to find the Total Effectiveness by using equation 2. And then the ETD calculation is done using equation 3[6].

$$TE_k = \sum ARP_j E_{jk} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Information:

TE_k = Total efektivitas of each action

ARP = Aggregate Risk Priority value

E_{jk} = The relationship of each action and each source of risk

TABLE 16. DEGREE OF DIFFICULTY

<i>Degree of Difficulty</i>	
Weight	Information
3	Mitigation actions are easy to implement
4	Mitigation actions are rather easy to implement
5	Mitigation actions are difficult to implement

$$ETD_k = TE_k / D_k \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Information:

TE_k = Total Effectiveness of each action

D_k = The degree of difficulty in performing each action

The results of the house of risk phase 2 calculation are presented in table 9. The results are then analyzed for priority levels of handling that must be done.

TABLE 17. HOUSE OF RISK PHASE 2 CALCULATION RESULTS

A_i	Total Effectiveness of Action (TE_k)	Degree of Difficulty performing action (D_k)	Effectiveness to difficulty ratio (ETD)	Rank
PA1	16695	5	3339	10
PA2	21630	5	4326	5
PA3	14805	4	3701.25	7
PA4	31500	4	7875	1
PA5	18417	5	3683.4	8
PA6	18945	3	6315	3

Ai	Total Effectiveness of Action (Tek)	Degree of Difficulty performing action (Dk)	Effectiveness to difficulty ratio (ETD)	Rank
PA7	15111	3	5037	4
PA8	20046	3	6682	2
PA9	17892	5	3578.4	9
PA10	10152	4	2538	11
PA11	9825	5	1965	12
PA12	14955	4	3738.75	6
PA13	7791	4	1947.75	13

Table 8 shows the results that the first treatment priority is P4. What is meant by handling with the P4 code is the strict inspection of incoming raw materials.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research and discussion that has been done, the following conclusions are obtained:

1. That the risks identified are 13 risk events and 9 dominant priority events that are the priority of handling.
2. From the dominant risk that occurs, handling with the first priority is in P4, which is more strictly inspected incoming fruits.

References

- [1] Ministry of Agriculture Indonesia, "Tree crop estate statistics of Indonesia 2015-2017," 2017.
- [2] M. M. Hanafi, "Risiko, Proses Manajemen Risiko, dan Enterprise Risk Management," in *Manajemen Risiko*, 2014, pp. 1–40.
- [3] X. C. Yuan, Y. M. Wei, B. Wang, and Z. Mi, "Risk management of extreme events under climate change," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 166, pp. 1169–1174, 2017.
- [4] P. Engelseth, I. N. Pujawan, and M. Ushada, "Continuous Handling of Uncertainty in Food Chains : Using the House of Risk Model in Ecosystems," pp. 363–373, 2018.
- [5] R. Utari and I. Baihaqi, "Perancangan Strategi Mitigasi Resiko Supply Chain di PT Atlas Copco Nusantara dengan Metoda House of Risk," pp. 1–10, 2015.
- [6] I. N. Pujawan and L. H. Geraldin, "House of risk: A model for proactive supply chain risk management," *Bus. Process Manag. J.*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 953–967, 2009.

